

String Standing Waves and Oscillator Solutions Without Newton's Second Law?

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Newton's second law or alternatively conservation of energy may be used in general to establish an equation of motion for a particle with rest mass in a nonrelativistic situation. In two special cases linked to periodic motion, namely an oscillating string tied at both ends and an oscillator, we try to argue that the dynamics of the problem follow from an orthogonality dot product (i.e. integral) of a function $y(x)$ for the string and $x(t)$ for the oscillator and its change i.e. dy/dx or dx/dt . This is equivalent to y and its change dy/dx (or x and dx/dt) forming the sides of a right angle triangle. This seems to be enough to solve these problems and suggests that only a first derivative is needed in such cases.

Waves on a String

Following (1) one may solve the standing wave on a string problem using Newton's second law:

$$d/dt \text{ d/dt } y(x,t) = F(x) = \text{Tension}(x+dx) - \text{Tension}(x) = T[dy(x+dx)/dx - T(dy(x)/dx)] \quad ((1))$$

Note: $dy/dx = \sin(\theta)$ i.e. $T\sin(\theta)$ is used to find the y component of tension.

Here T is constant tension. This leads to the wave equation:

$$d/dt \text{ d/dt } \text{partial } y(x,t) \text{ (1/vv)} = d/dx \text{ d/dx } \text{partial } y(x,t) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } v \text{ is constant velocity}$$

One may look for a separable solution so in space (or time):

$$d/dx \text{ d/dx } y_{\text{space}}(x) = B y_{\text{space}}(x) \quad \text{where } B \text{ is a constant} \quad ((3))$$

$d/dx \text{ d/dx } y_{\text{space}}(x)$, however, is proportional to net force on a small piece of string existing from x to $x+dx$ so ((3)) seems to indicate a spring or oscillator force. Thus one would expect the solution of spring which is what results showing the link between an oscillator and a standing wave on a string with the ends fastened.

In other words one has $\cos(kx)$ or $\sin(kx)$ type solutions.

Orthogonality

((1)) and ((2)) which follow from Newton's second law contain second derivatives, yet the solution $\sin(kx)$ or $\cos(kx)$ may be obtained only through a first derivative.

Consider the behaviour of the sides of a right angle triangle with a fixed hypotenuse of length 1. The sides are $\cos(\theta)$ and $\sin(\theta)$ so:

$$\cos(\theta) \cos(\theta) + \sin(\theta) \sin(\theta) = 1 \quad ((4))$$

One may see that $\frac{d}{d\theta} \cos(\theta) = -\sin(\theta)$ i.e. one function is the negative derivative of the other. This would be a solution even if one did not know about sin and cos i.e.

$$f(x)f'(x) + g(x)g'(x) = 1 \quad ((5)) \rightarrow 2f \frac{df}{dx} + 2g \frac{dg}{dx} = 0 \quad \text{A solution is } f = -\frac{dg}{dx} \text{ and } g = \frac{df}{dx}$$

An alternative way to consider this periodic function (sin, cos) we argue is to consider a radius of a circle and note that a tiny change is perpendicular to a given ray.

If one considers the product of $\sin(x)$ and $\cos(x)$ for a period:

$$\begin{aligned} \int (\text{over a period}) dx \cos(x) \sin(x) &= \int (\text{over a period}) dx \cos(x) \frac{d}{dx} \cos(x) (-1) \\ &= \int (\text{over a period}) (-1) \cdot \frac{d}{dx} (\cos(x) \cos(x)) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

In other words $\sin(x)$ and $\cos(x)$ are perpendicular functions and by ((5)) one is the first derivative of the other up to a minus or positive sign.

This seems to be enough to define $\sin(x)$ or $\cos(x)$ and we argue that it should be enough to solve certain periodic problems like a standing wave on a string with fastened ends or an oscillator.

Oscillator and Standing Wave on a String

As argued in the first section the standing wave on the string is really an oscillator problem. The oscillator in turn may be written as a conservation of energy equation from Newton:

$$.5m \dot{v}^2 + .5kx^2 = E \quad ((6))$$

This equation, however, is nothing more than an inner product. The vector is:

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \dot{v}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{k} x \right) \quad ((7))$$

For a periodic solution which keeps this vector constant $\sin(\omega t)$ or $\cos(\omega t)$ is a solution from the periodic behaviour of these functions. ((6)) is a special instance of Newton's energy conservation because v and x are of the same power, but we argue this special case may be obtained without knowledge of Newton's second law or conservation of energy. The same holds for the standing wave on a string with fastened ends. These two problems represent a periodic situation such that a function $x(t)$ (oscillator) or $y(x)$ string and its derivative $\frac{dx}{dt}$ (oscillator) $\frac{dy}{dx}$ string are orthogonal over a period (i.e. when multiplied and integrated over a period).

Even though these are special cases, both related to periodicity, we argue that there may be cases in nature which do not require Newton's second law (even though it also gives the result). Knowledge of the special periodicity involved (i.e. one for which the function and its derivative are orthogonal) seems to be enough.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Newton's second law or conservation of energy may be used to solve nonrelativistic problems. For two special cases, a standing wave on a string with fastened ends or an oscillator, we argue that periodicity with a function being orthogonal to its derivative is enough to solve the problem. In other words the properties of $\sin(x)$, $\cos(x)$ are enough to make them solutions of the problem without recourse to Newton's laws. (Newton's laws, however, also yield the solution.) They, however, require second derivatives while the orthogonality of $\sin(x)$ and $d\sin(x)/dx$ only requires a first derivative. In other words, we suggest that periodic solutions to certain problems follow from the nature of the periodicity in the problem.

References

1. Fowler, M. Analyzing Waves on a String (U. of Virginia)
<https://galileo.phys.virginia.edu/classes/152.mf1i.spring02/AnalyzingWaves.htm>